

Information Discrepancy In Newton's Second Law and the Lagrangian-Action And Consequences for the Quantum Free Particle Wavefunction

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Newton's second law for a conservative force is: $dp/dt = -dV/dx$. Mathematically, one may transform this, using integration by parts, into a function: $\int dt L(x, v(x)) = 0$, where $v(x)=dx/dt$, such that: $d/dt dL/dv - dL/dx = 0$. For the case of $V(x)=0$, $L = m_0 v^2/2$ nonrelativistically and $L = -m_0 c^2 \sqrt{1-v^2/c^2}$ relativistically.

We note that in the case of $p=\text{constant}$, Newton's law does not provide information about m_0 and v separately, but only about p . Thus, Newton's second law with no initial condition holds for all $p=m_0 v_1=m_0 v_2$ etc and in fact for any p magnitude value and simply states that p is a constant. The L Lagrangian function, however, requires two pieces of information, m_0 and v , both relativistically and nonrelativistically and so we argue that there is an information discrepancy, even though the Lagrangian may be used to obtain Newton's second law.

In order to deal with this discrepancy in the constant p case, we suggest that the basic information: x, t, p, E, m_0 and v may be expressed in terms of x, t, p, E because $v = p/E$ (relativistic object with mass) and $E^2 + p^2 c^2 = m_0^2 c^4$. In particular $A = Lt = -Et + px$ both relativistically and nonrelativistically. Here one sees a natural separation of px such that no m_0 or v information is present in this term. This information is consistent with Newton's second law. In fact, for p constant: $A = d/dx \text{ partial } A = p = d/dx px$. The latter contains all of the information of Newton's second law.

Given that d/dx is a generator of translations and that formally one may evaluate $d/dx (px)$ at any x , one is tempted to create an eigenfunction, $\exp(ipx)$, which neither grows or shrinks indefinitely. At first, it is not clear how such a function may be used, but if one considers the classical $P(x)dx = dx/L$, where L is length, then this is really the statement of arranging a non-moving object in L . In such a case, a composite p and $-p$ would be equivalent to a non-moving object and $\exp(ipx)/\sqrt{L} \exp(-ipx)/\sqrt{L}$ (i.e. an AND probability situation) would yield $1/L$.

We also note that for a free particle, $dp/dt=v dp/dx=0$, but that $d/dx (px) = p$ is a different math statement. It is consistent with the idea of p being a constant in space (the same idea as Newton's second law), but it also implies a flow or flux in space, namely p as an energy flux. Thus, we argue that $d/dx (px)$ is a more general statement than Newton's second law $dp/dx=0$ for a free particle. Extending $d/dx (px)$ to $\exp(ipx)$ allows one to solve problems, such as 2-slit interference or one dimensional reflection-refraction which cannot be solved using Newtonian mechanics.

Newton's Second Law and the Lagrangian - Information Discrepancy

Newton's second law: $dp/dt = \text{Force}(x)$ ((1))

holds both relativistically and nonrelativistically, but for the former $p=m_0 v/\sqrt{1-v^2/c^2}$, while for the latter, $p=m_0 v$. For a conservative force, $F=-dV/dx$ and for no force, $F=0$. Then:

$$dp/dt = 0 \text{ and } p = \text{constant} \quad ((2))$$

If one has no information about initial conditions, then p may take on any real value, positive or negative. That is the extent of the information. Furthermore, if $p =$ a particular constant, there are still many m_0, v combinations which yield the same p , both relativistically and nonrelativistically.

Next, one may consider an Action-Lagrangian formalism strictly from a math point of view. Given that one has dp/dt , and that $v = dx/dt$ if one had a function: $L(x, v(x), t)$ and varied it, then $x \rightarrow x + \delta x$, $v \rightarrow v + \delta v$ so one would have: $dL/dx \text{ partial } \delta x + dL/dv \text{ partial } \delta v$ if $L(x, v(x))$. Now: $\delta v = \delta dx/dt$ and if one may interchange δ and d/dt then one may use integration by parts. Thus, dL/dv must equal p so that integration by parts brings $-d/dt$ to act on p . This then leads to the Lagrangian formalism:

$$\Delta \int dt L(x, v(x)) = 0 \quad ((3)) \text{ so}$$

$$d/dt dL/dv - dL/dx = 0 \quad ((4))$$

((4)) is Newton's second law. The problem, from an information point of view, is that:

$$L = .5m_0 v^2 \text{ nonrelativistically and } L = -m_0 \sqrt{1-v^2/c^2} \text{ relativistically} \quad ((5a))$$

This means that originally one deals with p only in Newton's second law and now in the Lagrangian approach one requires m_0 and v as two pieces of information. It is not clear why this extra information is needed. Ultimately, the Lagrangian yields an equation only containing p , but we argue that one should see this reduced information already at the Lagrangian or Action (i.e. $\int dt L$) level.

In the nonrelativistic case, one may see why the Lagrangian requires extra information. Given Newton's second law: $dp/dt = F$, then:

$$dp = F dt = F v dx \rightarrow \int F dx = \int dp/v \quad ((5b))$$

Thus, one has two pieces of information now, namely p and v and one needs to link the two variables in order to perform the integral. Thus, integrating brings in the notion of two pieces of information, m_0 and v . Taking the derivative brings one back to Newton's second law. Thus, extra information may appear through integration.

For a constant p , $\int L dt = Lt$. In classical physics, the relevant information is x, t, m_0, v, E and p . The information x, t, p and E , however, is enough to obtain m_0 and v . For instance, if $x=0$ at $t=0$, the $v=x/t$ or $p/E=v$ (relativistic particle with rest mass) and $E^2 + p^2 c^2 = m_0^2 c^4$. Thus, the Action should be writable in terms of x, t, p and E . In fact, both relativistically and nonrelativistically one has:

$$\text{Action} = -Et + px \text{ for a free particle} \quad ((6))$$

Resolving the Information Discrepancy

((6)) allows one to resolve the information discrepancy. Newton's second law only contains p and indicates that it is a constant (for a free particle). The part of the action which contains precisely this same information is px . One may write:

$$d/dx (px) = p \quad ((7)) \quad \text{for } p = \text{constant}$$

((7)) contains all of the information of Newton's second law for the free particle. Thus, one starts with Newton's second law, creates a function L (Lagrangian) which requires more information, but then rewriting this in terms of E, p, x, t with $x/t=v$ for a free particle, one can take part of this which contains exactly the same information as Newton's second law if one takes d/dx of this piece.

Translational Invariance

One might wish to stop with $d/dx (px) = p$. One may note, however, that d/dx is the translational operator and that formally $d/dx f(x)$ should be evaluated at a specific x value. $d/dx (px)$ holds for all x values. This seems to suggest creating an eigenfunction which neither grows or shrinks indefinitely, i.e.

$$d/dx \exp(ipx) = ip \exp(ipx) \quad ((8))$$

At first glance, this eigenfunction $\exp(ipx)$, which contains an intrinsic length \hbar/p , where \hbar is a constant needed to allow for appropriate units, i.e. px should really be px/\hbar , does not seem to have any relevance.

One may note that classically, $P(x)dx = C/v(x) dx$ is used to describe probability based on the time a particle spends in a constant dx . For $v(x)=\text{constant}$, one has $P(x)dx = dx/L$. This, however, describes a motionless particle that is distributed in L . The fact that this holds for a motionless particle seems to call into question the idea that Δt is really a probability. Rather, $P(x)=1/L$ is simply a uniform distribution for a motionless object. One may create a motionless object from a composite $P_d(p,x)P_d(-p,x)$ i.e. $\exp(ipx)/\sqrt{L} \exp(-ipx)/\sqrt{L}$. Thus, $\exp(ipx)$ may represent a kind of dynamic probability.

In other words, one obtains the quantum mechanical free particle wavefunction $\exp(ipx)$ through considerations of part of the function $t L(v,x)$ written in terms of E, p, x, t with $x/t=v$ which contains the same information as Newton's second law. In this case, however, instead of treating p as a constant in time, one treats it as a constant in space, which is also the case for a free particle. In particular, for a free particle:

$$dp/dt=0 \quad \text{but} \quad dp/dx=0 \quad ((9)) \quad dp/dt = dp/dx dx/dt = 0 \quad \text{so} \quad dp/dx = 0$$

The piece of the free particle action, however, is px not p . This then leads to the notion of an operator d/dx action on a function of x and so one may extend this idea to that of an eigenfunction in x .

Px by Itself?

Given that the Action approach is strictly a math one, one could a priori point out that:

$d/dx (px) = p$ without needing to mention the Lagrangian or action at all. The d/dx derivative is needed to show that p is a constant. The above arguments may then be used to obtain $\exp(ipx)$.

Alternatively, one could write: $d/dt (pt) = p$.

This would seem to imply that one has an eigenfunction $\exp(ipt)$. If one tried to link this to classical probability of a motionless particle, then one would have this motionless particle appearing out of nowhere at different times (each with the same probability). This would be broken into a $p, -p$ pair appearing out of nowhere at time t together.

This does not seem to correspond to the physical situation of a particle which exists for all times. Thus, the $d/dx (px)$ interpretation seems to apply at least to usual physical situations.

The next question seems to be: Why not simply use Newton's $dp/dx = 0$ instead of $d/dx (px) = p$? Both math statements imply that p is a constant. The statement $d/dx (px) = p$ seems to indicate a flow, i.e. p as an energy flux, as well as showing that it is a constant. In other words, there are two pieces of physics linked with p , namely that it is constant and that there is energy flow in space. This seems to be a more general statement than Newton's dp/dx statement. In fact, using $d/dx (px)$ and extending this to $\exp(ipx)$ allows one to solve physical problems, such as 2-slit interference and one dimensional reflection-refraction which cannot be solved using Newtonian mechanics.

Link with Special Relativity for a Constant p

We note that the above arguments used to create $A = -Et + px$ for a free particle, namely $x/t = v$ are linked to the idea of a rest particle seen from different frames moving at constant v . In particular, m_0 at $x = x_0$ at t_0 becomes E', p' at $x'/t' = v$. Thus, the condition $x/t = v$ seems to be a special relativistic one. One may further note that $-Et + px$ is a Lorentz invariant.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we try to argue that Newton's second law for a free particle only deals with the variable p , i.e. $dp/dt = 0$. If one creates an action Lt , then both relativistically and nonrelativistically one has two pieces of information m_0, v and this is inconsistent with the one information piece, p , which appears in $dp/dt = 0$. Of course, applying $d/dt dL/dv - dL/dx = 0$ yields an equation in p , i.e. $dp/dt = 0$, but L itself contains extra information. We note that Lt for a free particle may be

written in terms of p, E, x, t . This yields information about $v (=x/t)$ and m_0 . In such a case, one obtains: $A = -Et + px$ both relativistically and nonrelativistically. If one considers the term which contains the same information as Newton's second law, then one has: px . In particular: $d(px)/dx = p$. Given that d/dx is a translational operator and that $d/dx f(x)$ should generally be evaluated at a given x point, one may generalize this result and create an eigenvalue equation with $\exp(ipx)$ as an eigenfunction which does not grow or shrink.

It seems, however, that $\exp(ipx)$ has no classical meaning. In classical physics, one uses $P(x)dx = C/v(x) dx$, where $v(x)$ is velocity. For a constant $v(x)$, one has $P(x)=1/L$, where L is length. This equation, however, holds for the distribution of motionless objects in keeping with classical probability. This brings into question the idea that dt is proportional to the probability of a moving object. If $P(x)=1/L$ is the distribution of a motionless object, then a $p, -p$ pair is also motionless, but this requires an AND probability product which $\exp(ipx)\exp(-ipx)$ supplies.

Thus, we argue that by only considering the information in Lt for a free particle which matches that in Newton's second law, one obtains px so that $d/dx px = p$. From this one may generalize to an eigenfunction $\exp(ipx)$ which seems to have the interpretation of dynamical probability if one consider $P(x)=1/L$ as describing the arrangement of static objects in L . $\exp(ipx)$, however, is also the quantum free particle wavefunction.